

13357_UKR**Spatial-time analysis of the inhomogeneity of the surface temperature of the Kyiv to locate “heat islands”*****R.Y. Okhrimchuk, V.I. Zatserkovnyy, P.O. Berezina** (*Institute of Geology, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv*)**SUMMARY**

The paper proposes a spatial-time analysis of the results of the temperatures fluctuations of the Kyiv and surrounding suburban areas in locating “heat islands” in the period from 1984 to 2018. On the basis of the results of the analysis, it was found that within the city zone the cyclical course of the change in the heat flow is significantly different in relation to other types of territories. The observed effect is due to a large amount of secondary heat, which is typical for urban areas. Also, based on the results, the dynamics of the development of the " heat islands" of the city of Kyiv was investigated.

Просторово-часовий аналіз неоднорідності температури поверхні міста Києва для виділення «теплових островів»***Р.Ю. Охрімчук, В.І. Зацерковний, П.О. Березіна** (*ІНІ "Інститут геології" Київського національного університету імені Тараса Шевченка*)**РЕЗІОМЕ**

В даній роботі запропонований просторово-часовий аналіз результатів досліджень неоднорідності температур поверхні міста Київ та прилеглих приміських територій в період з 1984 до 2018 р. для виділення “теплових островів”. За отриманими результатами аналізу було виявлено, що в межах міської зони циклічний хід зміни теплового потоку суттєво відрізняється по відношенню до інших типів територій. Спостережений ефект обумовлений великою кількістю вторинного тепла, яке є характерним для урбанізованої територій. Також за отриманими результатами була досліджена динаміка розвитку “теплових островів” міста Київ.

Introduction

For urban areas, the so-called "heat islands" are typical to appear and it is connected with differentiation of near-surface temperatures between the center of the city and its periphery. Reduction of green zones areas in the central part of the city and increase of the construction density leads to a growth of near-surface temperature. In turn, this leads to a deterioration of the ecological situation and comfortable living of urban population

Statement of the main contents

The topicality of the topic is determined by the significant growth rates of urbanization. Scientists predicted that by 2050 70% of the world's population will live in cities. The city has a significant impact on the climate, creating on its individual streets and squares the unique microclimatic conditions determined by constructing process, street coverage, distribution of green plantation areas, etc. Roofs and walls of buildings, asphalt roads, paths and other elements of the city's infrastructure absorbing radiation heat up throughout the day more strongly than the soil, grass, and give warm air especially in the evening. The city's surface compared with vegetation or other natural coatings reflects a smaller amount of radiation to the atmosphere, but it absorbs more radiation and accumulates it. This leads to an increase in the temperature of the adjacent areas. At the same time, in the city to the scattered radiation is added radiation reflected by walls, pavement and asphalt caused by urban geometry and the ability of building materials to accumulate heat.

Urban geometry prevents the release of urban heat accumulated in the atmosphere. The system of city streets and squares leads to changes in the direction of the wind in the city. In general, the wind speed in the city decreases but in narrow streets, it is increasing. The wind is mainly directed along the streets, which causes the appearance of dust vortices on these streets and neighboring intersections.

City zones as a rule have less humidity than natural landscapes due to the coverage of streets and drainage of water into sewers. As the city's territory is heated more than the surrounding area over the city the convection increases and more clouds are formed, which in turn reduces the number of clear days. As a result there is an increase in rainfall over the city. Reducing the level of humidity in the built-up areas leads to the formation of a dry surface, which in consequence increases the air temperature of the adjacent area. The thermos-physical properties of surfaces and their thermodynamic processes are related to the spatial heterogeneity of air temperature within the city's territory, which is characterized by a variety of factors that determine the nature and intensity of the transformation of the surface air layer. Anthropogenic heat appearing as a result of functioning of cars, air conditioners, industrial facilities and various other man-made sources, causes an increase in the temperature of the surrounding environment and as a result contributes to the sharp differentiation of temperatures especially in winter.

One or several closed isotherms characterize the temperature area above the city; these isotherms are called "urban heat islands". As the city grows up the temperature in it increases. The rate of urbanization in Kyiv is rather high despite the overall negative growth in Ukraine. As of 01.02.2018 the city accounted for 2.93 million [1].

The consequence of the difference in temperature between urban and rural areas is the deterioration of the health of the city's inhabitants which manifests itself in overheating and heat stress in it. Due to the negative impact on the health and comfort of the inhabitants the energy consumption and air quality "heat islands" considerably decrease the quality of life in the city.

Therefore control over the temperature of the earth's surface of the city is extremely important. Modern researches are carried out with the help of methods of remote sensing of the Earth.

Based on the results of the analysis it was found that within the city zone the cyclical course of the change in the heat flow significantly differs from other types of territories. The main tasks of the work were to review the literature on this issue, to obtain Landsat satellite images for the 34-year period, to create an algorithm for the preliminary processing of satellite images and to obtain maps of the temperature of the earth's surface and the intensity of city heat islands, to implement the algorithm

using the Matlab software language, to interpret and visualize data results with the help of ArcGIS software to find interdependencies and regularities.

Thermal infrared remote sensing of the Earth is widely used to detect changes in the temperature of the earth's surface thanks to its wide coverage, repeated cycle of the orbit and low cost. However, such images typically contain clouds, aerosols, systematic errors and missed values. In order to avoid errors, a satellite image set with close to zero cloudiness was selected in the study. Table 1 shows the selected dates and series of Landsat satellites downloaded from the USGS Earth Explorer Web Platform for Kyiv city in line with the World Wide Reference System (WRS2 path 181, row 025) in the Universal Mercator's Transversal Projection (UTM).

Table 1

Satellite photos (images and their metadata)					
Satellite	Sensor	Distinctness, m	Cloudiness, %	Receipt date	Receipt time
Landsat 8	OLI & TIRS	30 (120 TIRS)	0.00	2018-02-25	08:49:11
				2014-10-28	08:49:37
Landsat 5	TM	30 (100 TIRS)	1.00 0.00 0.00	2004-08-29	08:32:48
				1994-07-17	08:07:31
				1984-11-26	08:19:18

The Thematic Mapper (TM) sensor on board of Landsat 5 Satellite receives images in seven spectral bands, six of which cover the visible and infrared short-wave particles of electromagnetic spectrum (0.5-2.5 microns) and one thermal infrared range (10.4-12.5 micron). The Landsat 8 is equipped with Operational Land Imager (OLI) and Thermal Infrared (TIRS) sensors. TIRS already has two channels in the thermal range: 10th channel within 10.60-11.19 microns and 11th channel within 11.50-12.51 microns.

The received Landsat Collection Level-1 products from the Earth Explorer USGS platform are already geometrically and radio-metrically calibrated.

The images are further processed to obtain the values of the energy brightness of the upper atmosphere according to the formula (1) for Landsat 5 and formula (2) for Landsat 8. The reflection coefficient for Landsat 5 is obtained by the formula (3); for Landsat 8 by the formula (4) [2, 3]:

$$L_{\lambda} = \left(\frac{L_{MAX_{\lambda}} - L_{MIN_{\lambda}}}{Q_{calMAX}} \right) Q_{cal} + L_{MIN_{\lambda}}, \quad (1)$$

$$L_{\lambda} = M_{\lambda} Q_{cal} + A_{\lambda}, \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_{\lambda} = \frac{\pi L_{\lambda} d_s^2}{E_{0\lambda} \cos \theta}, \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_{\lambda} = M_{\rho} Q_{cal} + A_{\rho} \quad (4)$$

where Q_{cal} – calibrated pixel value;

$L_{MIN_{\lambda}}$ – energy brightness that corresponds to Q_{calMIN} ;

$L_{MAX_{\lambda}}$ – energy brightness that corresponds to Q_{calMAX} ;

d_s – distance from Earth to Sun in astronomical units;

$E_{0\lambda}$ – exo-atmospheric solar radiation in the channel λ (in $W/(m^2 \cdot mm)$);

θ – zenithal angle of the Sun;

M_{λ} , M_{ρ} , A_{λ} , A_{ρ} – channel factors of multiplicative and additive scaling from metadata respectively.

The transformation of the spectral energy brightness into the brightness temperature on the satellite is carried out according to the formula (5)

$$T_B = \frac{K_2}{\ln\left(\frac{K_1}{L_\lambda} + 1\right)} \quad (5)$$

where T_B is effective temperature on the satellite (kelvin);

L_λ – spectral energy brightness (W/(m²·sr·microns));

K_2 та K_1 – gauge constants.

However, the value of the temperature of brightness is not the temperature of the earth's surface, but is most likely a mixed signal, which includes the Earth's radiation energy, ascending and descending energy brightness. Radiation power of the earth's surface is one of the main parameters for obtaining the temperature of the earth's surface. In this study, a method for evaluating the radiation ability presented in the paper [4] is used. The general formula for calculating the temperature of the earth's surface is:

$$T = \frac{T_B}{1 + \left(\lambda \times \frac{T_B}{\rho}\right) \ln \varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

where λ – the length of energy brightness wave;

$\rho = h \cdot c / \sigma$ (1.438 × 10⁻² m·kelvin);

σ – Boltzmann constant (1.38 × 10⁻²³ joule/kelvin);

h – Plank's constant (6.626 × 10⁻³⁴ joule·sec);

c – light speed in vacuum (2.998 × 10⁸ m/sec).

For Landsat 5 channels $\lambda=11.5$ microns; for 10th channel Landsat 8 $\lambda=10.8$ microns, 11th channel $\lambda=12$ microns.

For evaluation of the value of the radiation power in the work the following method was used – method of limit values of the standardized index of plant cover differences (NDVI) [5]. NDVI, which is received according to the formula (7):

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (7)$$

where NIR – channel of near infra-red radiation, Red – the channel of red radiation.

Conclusions

The main factors influencing the formation of indicators of the intensity of "heat islands" are the degree of urbanization (the total area of construction, population numbers, the presence of industrial objects and transport nodes), the geometry of the city territory, the physical environment and the nature of human activity. According to the results of the study it has been found that characteristics such as the underlying surface, the type of land use and vegetation cover also directly affect its formation [6].

According to the results of the analysis of satellite images, weather factors affect the visualization of "heat islands". When investigating the effects of various weather conditions on their formation, it turned out that wind speed, precipitation and cloudiness are the main factors of influence. Therefore, some "heat islands" may not be obvious or with values that deviates from the real values of measurements made by ground devices. Terrestrial meteorological observations are required to verify the accuracy of satellite imagery analysis.

The conducted analysis of space images in the thermal infrared range can serve as the basis for studying the environment in cities and the definition of "heat islands". Remote sensing reduces cost and at the same time allows you to increase the research area.

According to the results of the conducted space-time analysis it was determined that appearance and formation of the “heat islands” is historically typical for Shevchenkivskiyi, Dniprovskiyi, Obolonskiy and Sviatoshinskiy districts where there is a high density of urban construction. Abnormal values of the surface temperatures are typical for the areas where powerful plants are located as well as transport conjunctions with intensive traffic and densely build up areas. For the areas with high vegetation and high NDVI indicator lower temperatures are more typical than in districts with missing variegated vegetation. Parks, water objects, green plantations play the role of elements that stabilize surface temperature and counteract the emergence of “heat islands”.

The list of used literature

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